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“CHER PAPA”

“I want to treat my students the same way I hope my son’s teachers will treat him.”

I am blessed of being a teacher and being a father at the same time. Both roles constantly challenge me, humble me, and fill me with happiness. They are remarkably similar. They need a lot of patience, presence, and the willingness to make sacrifices for others' development. However, if there's one lesson my experience has taught me, it's that being successful in one role does not automatically translate into success in the other.

As a teacher I have spent numerous hours developing lessons while mentoring my students and offering encouragement when they need it. That is why, my heart frequently breaks whenever I see the misunderstood, unseen and unheard young minds. One of my goals is to provide them some structure, caring attention and belief in their worth, which they may not receive at home. But now, as a father, I realize how easy it is to drain so much of myself into other people's children that I unintentionally neglecting my own child.

I have observed that there are great teachers who have develop poor family relationships specially with their children. There are teachers who inspire their students in class, yet are misunderstood, resented, or even rebelled against by their own children. I can only speculate that this may come either from the emotional drain of continuously committing to others or from the sheer amount of time the profession demands from a teacher. God knows I do want to become an inspiring instructor, but I don't want my teaching to be a hindrance to being a good father either.

Being a father brings exhaustion but at the same time brings joy and a deep sense of accomplishment. The experience of watching my child reach developmental goals such as their first smile, first words and first graduation holds a sacred value. Like teaching, fatherhood delivers many small victories which other people fail to recognize yet these moments define a person's life. Every bedtime story, every hug and kiss, every cry, every stumble and every fall – they all matter.

And yet, I struggle. The boundary between treating students as my children and I don't always know when to apply my teaching strategies to my parenting. My training teaches me to plan, observe, assess, adjust. However, there are times when my child requires more than a strategy; he needs me to be just his father. Students sometimes just need to feel safe, heard and be seen rather than receive from me mere classroom lecture.

I am slowly learning that the best parts of teaching (patience, encouragement and genuine care) can also be that of parenting. I want to treat my students the same way I hope my son's teachers will treat him. The key to success in both roles depends on my ability to remain present even though I may not always succeed perfectly; not just physically, but emotionally, spiritually, wholeheartedly. I need to grant myself the leeway to make mistakes, to be human. I will apologize whenever I fail to meet expectations. For whether in the classroom or at home, the goal isn't perfection—it's connection.

I now know that one key to success lies in my ability to maintain love and grace in both my teaching career and my fatherhood. Since becoming a teacher will help me become a better father and becoming a parent will make me a better teacher. Not because I'll always get it right, but because I'll never stop trying to love.

